

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Trends Analysis of Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever in Campurejo East Java, Indonesia 2019-2021

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ABSTRACT

Background: Dengue fever is a disease with a fairly high prevalence in Indonesia. Currently, dengue fever is a public health problem in Indonesia, with a tendency to increase in number of cases and spread. The aim of this study is to determine the pattern of dengue fever based trends at the Campurejo Health Center, Kediri City in 2019 to 2021. **Methods:** This is an observational descriptive study. The data collection is to collect the required data or information, including the data on dengue fever cases based on age, gender and place of residence, larva-free number data for each sub-district of the Campurejo Health Centre. **Results:** In 2019 The area with the highest number of cases is Bandar Kidul village (15 cases). In 2020, the areas with the most cases were Bandar Kidul village (16 cases) and Lirboyo village (13 cases). In 2021, The area with the highest number of cases is Bandar Kidul Village (9 cases). **Conclusion:** The number of dengue hemorrhagic fever cases will decrease between 2019 and 2021, and the areas with the highest number of cases will also change.

Keywords: Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever, Health Center, Prevalence, Trends Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF) is a disease caused by the dengue virus, which is transmitted by the *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes. It is one of several infectious diseases that pose health problems around the world, especially in developing countries (Sunaryanti & Iswahyuni, 2020). According to Lestari (2015), cited by (Dewi et al., 2019), dengue fever is a disease with a fairly high prevalence in Indonesia.

Dengue fever is not a new disease either, as it occurs almost every year with the change of seasons, from the rainy season to the dry season and vice versa. Currently, dengue fever is a public health problem in Indonesia, with a tendency to increase in number of cases and spread. Extraordinary dengue events usually occur in

endemic areas and are associated with the onset of the rainy season, resulting in increased dengue vector activity during the rainy season, which can lead to the transmission of dengue disease to humans via the *Aedes* vector (Wardani & Santjaka, 2017). Dengue can be transmitted from children under the age of 15 to adults (Butarbutar et al., 2019).

Based on data from around the world, Asia is the world's ranks first in the number of cases of dengue fever each year. According to the WHO, the highest number of dengue fever cases occurred in eight countries in Asia, namely Indonesia, Myanmar, Bangladesh, India, Maldives, Sri Lanka, Thailand and Timor Leste (Masrizal & Sari, 2016). According to the WHO, up to three billion people around the world are at risk of contracting dengue each year. According to 2018 WHO data, the incidence of dengue fever has

increased 30-fold, with 390 million dengue infections per year, of which 96 million were clinically classified as severe dengue over the past 50 years. Based on 2020 Health Profile data, the IR (incidence rate) per 100,000 population of dengue fever has fluctuated in 2011-2021.

The highest incidence rate of dengue fever occurred in 2016. In 2021, the incidence rate of dengue fever will decrease very drastically. However, it is not impossible that it will increase again the following year, as it did in 2018 towards 2019.

Based on data on dengue fever cases at the Campurejo Health Center, Kediri City in 2019, the number of cases was 52 cases, there was an increase of 54 cases in 2020 and there was a decrease in cases in 2021, namely 23 cases. Larva-free number data in 2021 in the 5 sub-districts under the Campurejo Health Center obtained an average of 94.32%.

According to the Indonesian Ministry of Health (2013) cited by (Kuwa & Sulastien, 2021) the larvae-free rate can be categorized as good if it reaches under 95%. So it could mean that larva-free number still does not meet the good category.

Although dengue cases have declined, climate change in Indonesia can change. This climate will affect the transmission patterns of vector-borne diseases such as dengue (Kuwa & Sulastien, 2021). Increases in temperature, rainfall and humidity are thought to increase the incidence of diseases that can infect humans, such as dengue fever and malaria. There is a link between the incidence of dengue fever and climate variability such as air temperature and humidity (Tuuk et al., 2021).

Therefore, the assessment of dengue fever needs to be carried out in more detail to see and map it based on the characteristics of age, gender and place of residence or regional map to get a clear picture of the distribution of cases where better prevention or intervention activities can then be carried out to minimise the spread of

dengue cases in the area. Work area of the Campurejo Health Centre.

The aim of this research is to determine the pattern of dengue fever trends at the Campurejo Health Center, Kediri City in 2019-2021.

METHODS

This is an observational descriptive study. The preparation stage for recording the list of secondary data to be collected. The data collection stage here is an activity to collect the required data or information, including the profile of the Campurejo health centres, history, organisational structure, data on 10 disease trends over the last 3 years, dengue fever programmes, data on dengue fever cases based on age, gender and place of residence, larva-free number data for each sub-district of the Campurejo health centre.

Data processing is carried out using the Geographic Information System (Quantum GIS) application, which aims at area mapping (spotmap). This application is available for free by the developer <https://www.qgis.org>. This mapping is intended to facilitate the explanation of the changes in the number of cases by region in Campurejo over three years, namely 2019, 2020 and 2021.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In 2019, the area has a number of dengue cases in the range of 13-15 cases. The area with the highest number of cases is Bandar Kidul village (15 cases).

The pink map shows the number of dengue cases in the range of 9-13 cases, namely in Banjarmlati Village (10 cases) and Lirboyo Village (12 cases), while the white map shows the number of dengue cases in the range of 0-8 cases, namely in Campurejo Village (8 cases) and Tamanan Village (7 cases). These areas are included in the high category.

Figure 1. Trends of Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever

In 2020, the areas with the most cases were Bandar Kidul village (16 cases) and Lirboyo village (13 cases). The pink map shows the number of dengue fever cases with a range of 10-12 cases, namely in Campurejo village (10 cases), while the white map shows the number of dengue fever cases with a range of 6-9 cases, namely in Banjarmlati village (9 cases) and Tamanan village (6 cases).

Based on the 2021 mapping results, we can see that Sub-districts in dark red indicate that the area has the highest number of dengue cases with a range of 6-9 cases. The area with the highest number of cases is Bandar Kidul Village (9 cases). The pink map shows the number of dengue cases with a range of 3-6 cases, namely in Banjarmlati village (5 cases) and Lirboyo village (4 cases). Meanwhile, the white map shows the number of dengue incidents with a range of 1-3 cases, namely in Campurejo village (2 cases) and Tamanan village (3 cases).

DHF cases in the Campurejo Community Health Centre work area in 2019-2021 were predominantly male, with a total of 79 out of 129 cases in the last three years. This is consistent with research (Novrita et al., 2017) showing a relationship between gender and dengue incidence. Previous research also showed that male respondents were 4.9 times more likely to have dengue fever than female respondents.

Research conducted by (Rojali & Amalia, 2020) shows that there is a significant relationship between gender and the incidence of dengue fever in RW 06, Ciracas Village, Ciracas District, East Jakarta in 2019. Men who are male have a 4.146 higher risk of contracting dengue fever compared to the female population.

The existence of a relationship between gender and the incidence of dengue fever is because according to Halstead's theory in Guha-Sapir & Schimmer (2005), the number of dengue sufferers who are male is higher than female due to immunity factors in the body. Women have a better immune response than men. This is

because the production of cytokine is higher in women than in men. This cytokine is a hormone that is responsible for regulating the intensity and duration of the immune response in a person's body.

Men also tend to be more mobile and work more, so it is possible that men travel to areas where dengue fever is endemic. There are several factors that could be related to the findings of this study, for example, men are known to be more active than women and therefore may reach mosquito breeding sites more often than women (Priesley et al., 2018).

DHF cases in the Campurejo Community Health Centre work area in 2019-2021 were experienced by people aged 0-35 years. DHF cases are predominantly experienced by children aged 0-16 years, with a total of 108 cases out of 129 cases in the last 3 years.

The results of the study conducted by (Sugiarti & Aulia, 2018) in the children's age group (0-11 years) were 4 persons with DHF severity I, 3 persons with DHF severity II and DHF severity III and IV respectively. 1 person each. This is because the younger the age of the dengue fever patient, the higher the mortality. Susceptibility to shock is relatively constant between 4 and 12 years of age and decreases in adolescence.

A study by (Rojali & Amalia, 2020) shows that there is a significant relationship between age groups and the incidence of dengue fever. This is in line with Sunarsih's research which shows that there is a relationship between age and the incidence of dengue fever in the working area of Tlogosari Wetan Community Health Centre (Sunarsih, 2017).

This research shows that the under-15 age group is more susceptible to the disease, and that children's activities are more outside the home, such as spending more time at school in the morning, or playing for several hours or even most of the day in conditions and at times that put them at risk mosquito bites that transmit dengue fever.

Soedarmo (2002) also said that the capillary endothelium of younger children is more susceptible to the release of cytokines, causing an increase in capillary permeability. In research by Rusnadi Kurniawan (2009) cited by (Sigalingging et al., 2021), children aged 5-10 years have a 4.3 times higher risk of developing dengue fever than other age groups.

Based on the mapping results, it is known that the highest number of dengue cases in the Campurejo Community Health Centre work area during 2019-2021 occurred in Bandar Kidul Village with a total of 40 cases, but the lowest percentage of larva-free number was in Tamanan Village. Based on observations, Tamanan Village has a high population density, many houses are too close together, and population mobility is high. In addition, puddles of water always flood the area during the rainy season.

The close proximity of houses makes it easier for mosquitoes to transmit dengue virus to the environment around the house, given that mosquitoes have a maximum flight distance of 100 metres. Residential areas with high population density only act as a supporting factor in the spread of dengue (Ratnasari et al., 2018).

Research conducted by Ratnasari in the city of Semarang shows that there is a significant relationship between the presence of stagnant water and the incidence of dengue fever. The eggs, larvae and pupae of the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito grow and develop in water. The main breeding site for the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito is clean water reservoirs, not standing water on the ground (Ratnasari et al., 2018).

Population mobility between regions also contributes to the incidence of disease (Achmadi, U. F. 2011). High population mobility occurs not only in urban areas with advanced transport and information facilities. It also occurs in villages and on islands. This is because it is influenced by the professions and activities of the population, which require mobility both

within and outside the area of residence. In addition to the positive impact, high mobility also has a negative impact by causing the spread of diseases from one area to another due to population movement (Hidayat & Nasriah, 2019).

The percentage of larva-free number in the Campurejo Community Health Centre working area in 2019-2021, of which 2 sub-districts, namely Banjarmlati and Bandarkidul sub-districts, experienced an increase, but the other 3 sub-districts fluctuated during 2019-2021. The average larva-free number over the last 3 years is still <95%, there is only one sub-district whose larva-free number meets the target, namely Banjarmlati Village. A low larva-free number can potentially increase the transmission of dengue hemorrhagic fever (Badrah & Hidayah, 2010).

CONCLUSIONS

Dengue hemorrhagic fever cases with larva-free number, which are still low in the Campurejo Health Centre work area in 2019-2021, have the dominant cause of the problem, namely the lack of detailed recapitulation of DHF case data. There is no regional mapping data (spotmap), although regional mapping makes it easier to track cases that can be used as evaluation material for dengue prevention.

The gender distribution of dengue fever cases in the Campurejo Community Health Centre area is male-dominated with a total of 79 out of 129 cases. Research shows that there is a relationship between gender and the incidence of dengue fever. This is because men are more active than women and therefore reach mosquito breeding sites more often.

The age distribution of dengue fever cases in the Campurejo Health Centre area is predominantly in the 0-16 age group. This is because research shows that children between the ages of 5 and 10 are 4.3 times more likely to contract dengue than other age groups.

The mapping results show that during 2019-2021, the highest number of dengue fever cases in the Campurejo Community Health Centre work area occurred in Bandar Kidul sub-district, with a total of 40 cases. The number of cases is inversely proportional to the percentage of *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes that are free of larvae. The lowest percentage of larvae free was found in Tamanan subdistrict, where high population density, many houses too close together, high population mobility and water stagnation during the rainy season were observed, making it easier for vector risks to arise and transmit dengue fever.

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